

A REVIEW ON TRIVRUTADI GUTIKA AND ITS CONTENTS

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Trivrutadi Gutika* is a classical Ayurvedic formulation mentioned in *Chakradatta* under *Udavarta Chikitsa*. The formulation primarily comprises *Trivrut* (*Operculina turpethum*), *Pippali* (*Piper longum*), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*), and *Guda* (jaggery). *Udavarta*, characterized by upward movement of *Apana Vata* leading to abdominal distension, constipation, and pain, is a condition demanding timely intervention. *Trivrutadi Gutika* is indicated for its *Anulomana* (carminative), *Bhedana* (purgative), and *Vata-anulomaka* properties. **Material & Methods:** In the present study a critical analysis based on ingredients and probable mode of action of *Trivrutadi gutika* were done based on classical and contemporary research work from classical books, journals, online data base etc. **Results:** The formulation exhibits synergistic action. *Trivrut* acts as a gentle purgative (*sukha virechana*) and relieves *Vibandha* (constipation). *Pippali* enhances digestion (*Agnideepana*) and bioavailability. *Haritaki* offers mild laxative, anti-inflammatory, and *Vata-shamaka* properties. *Guda* functions as a palatable binding medium with *Anulomana* effect. Collectively, the *Gutika* restores the downward movement of *Apana Vata* and relieves *Udavarta*. **Discussion & Conclusion:** *Trivrutadi Gutika*, with its combined *Bhedana* and *Anulomana* effects, plays a vital role in breaking the *Samprapti* of *Udavarta*. The formulation balances Vata and normalizes bowel evacuation, making it effective not only in *Udavarta* but also in conditions like chronic constipation, flatulence, and abdominal discomfort.

KEYWORDS: *Trivrutadi Gutika*, *Udavarta*, *Apana Vata*, *Anulomana*, *Bhedana*, Constipation.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, emphasizes the holistic management of disorders through *Ahara* (diet), *Vihara* (lifestyle), and *Aushadhi* (medicine). Among the vast range of Ayurvedic formulations, *Trivrutadi Gutika* is a well-known compound preparation, described in *Chakradatta* under *Udavarta Chikitsa*.^[1] The formulation comprises *Trivrut* (*Operculina turpethum*), *Pippali* (*Piper longum*), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*), and *Guda* (jaggery), which together provide *Anulomana* (carminative) and *Bhedana* (purgative) effects, restoring the normal downward movement of *Apana Vata*.

Udavarta is a pathological condition characterized by upward movement of *Vata* resulting in symptoms such as constipation, abdominal distension, colic, and sometimes

systemic manifestations. Its pathogenesis (*Samprapti*) is mainly due to suppression or obstruction of natural urges, faulty diet, and lifestyle.^[2] Timely intervention with *Vata-anulomaka* and *Bhedana* drugs is emphasized for effective management.

The chief ingredient, *Trivrut* (*Operculina turpethum*), is categorized as a potent purgative (*Bhedana dravya*) in Ayurvedic literature.^[3] *Pippali* is renowned for its *Agnideepana* (digestive stimulant), *Rasayana* (rejuvenative), and bioavailability-enhancing properties.^[4] *Haritaki*, known as *Abhaya*, is a mild laxative with *Vata-kaphahara* action and is extensively used in *Vibandha* and gastrointestinal disorders.^[5] *Guda* not only acts as a palatable medium but also possesses mild *Anulomana* and nutritive qualities.^[6] Together,

these ingredients act synergistically to regulate bowel movements, relieve constipation, and normalize Vata. Hence, *Trivrutadi Gutika* is considered an effective formulation in *Udavarta* and related conditions like chronic constipation, flatulence, and indigestion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Classical Reference

Classical reference of this formulation is from *Chakradatta* of *Chakrapanidatta Udavarta chikitsa*

(28/6). The ingredients of *Trivrutadi Gutika* are as follows: *Trivruta*, *Pippali*, *Haritaki*, and *Guda*.

Method of Preparation of *Trivrutadi Gutika*

Trivruta churna 2 parts, *pippali churna* 4 parts, *haritaki churna* 5 parts and *guda* 11 parts are taken, then first melt the guda. Then add remain ingredients and made into pills; this is consumed along with lukewarm water, cures the *vidavibhanda*.

List of the Ingredients of *Trivrutadi Gutika*

Table 1: List of the Ingredients of *Trivrutadi Gutika*.

S.No.	Ingredients	Botanical Name	Family	Gana	Parts Used	Classical Names
1.	<i>Trivruta</i>	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> Silva Manso.	Convolvulaceae	<i>Bhedaniya, Shyamadi, Adhobhagahara</i>	Root bark	<i>Tribhandi, Triputa, Sarvanubhuti, Sarala, Nishotra, Rechani</i>
2.	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	Piperaceae	<i>Deepaniya, kantya, asthapanopaga, shirovirechanopaga, sheetaprashamana, shoolaprashamana, Kasahara, hikkaniyagraha, trptighna, vamanopaga, Pippalyadi, urdhavbhaghara, shirovirechana, trayushana, amalakyadi.</i>	Fruit, root	<i>Magadhi, krishna, kana, upakulya, shaundi, vaidehi, kola, teekshna tandula.</i>
3.	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Combretaceae	<i>Prajasthapan, Jwaraghna, Kushthaghna, Kasahara, Aamalakyadi, parushakadi, triphala</i>	Fruit	<i>Abhaya, Pathya, Kayastha, Pootana, Amrita, Haimavati, Avyatha, Chetaki, Shreyasi, Shiva, Vayastha, Vijaya, Jeevanti, Rohini</i>
4.	<i>Guda</i>	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	Gramineae	<i>Naveen guda- Vrushya, Guru, Snigdha, Vatanashak, Mutrashodhan, Na-ati-pittakara, Medakara, Kaphakara, Krimikara, Balakara, Swasakara. Purana guda- is Laghu, Pathya, Anbhishandi, Agnijanaka, Pusthikruta, Pittaghna, Madhur, Vrushya, Vataghna, Rak-tap rasadaka.</i>	-	-

Table 2: Properties of *Trivrutadi Gutika* Ingredients.

S.No.	Ingredients	Rasa	Guna	Vipaka	Veerya	Dosha Karmata
1.	<i>Trivruta</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Pittakaphashamaka</i>
2.	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, snigdha, Tikshna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Anushna sheeta</i>	<i>Kaphavatadhamaka</i>
3.	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Pancharasa (Alavana), Kashaya Pradhan</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Tridoshashamaka</i>
4.	<i>Guda</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Vata-pittashamaka</i>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Action of Each Drug

1. *Trivruta*^[7]

Rogagnata: *Kustha, Visarpa, Krimi, Vibandha, Vrana, Visha Rogas, Kamala, Arbud, Galaganda, Granthi, Daha, Udara, Bhagandhara, Nadivrana, Pandu, Raktapitta, VataRakta, Prameha, Stoulya, Jwara, Kasa, Swasa, Yakrit Rogas, Plihavridhi, Yoni Rogas, Shotha, and Grahani.*

Karma: *Rechana, vatanuloman, pittakaphahara.*

Chemical composition: An ether insoluble glycoside-turpethin, 2 other soluble glycosides- α , β turpethins Coumarin scopoletin along with sugars glucose, rhamnose, fructose 4^l-O-methyl apigenin, luteolin & its derivative, gentisic, protocatechuic, vanillic, p-coumaric, metiolic, ferulic acids, turpethinic acids A,B,C,D & E, saponins are major components derived from various parts of this plant.

Pharmacological and clinical study of *Trivruta*: Anti-bacterial activity, Anti-inflammatory activity, Anti-secretory activity, Anti-microbial activity, Anti-diabetic activity, Hepato-protective activity, Cytotoxic activity.

2. *Pippali*^[8]

Rogagnata: *Shotha, sheetayukta Vedana, mastisk daurbalya, vatavyadhi, aruchi, agnimandhya, ajeerna, vibandha, gulma, udarashoola, arsha, yakridvikara, pleehavridhi, krimiroga, hrid-daurbalya, pandu, raktavikara, amvata, vatarakta, kasa, shwasa, hikka, kshaya, yakshma, mootravikara, shukradaurbalya, kustha, jeerna jwara, vishamjwara, samanya daurbalya, rajorodha, kashthaprasav.*

Karma: *Raktokleshaka, jantughna, shirovirechana, Medhya, vatahara, Deepana, vatanulomana, shooplaprashamana, pleehavridhihara, yakriduttejaka, meidurechana, krimighna, uttejaka, raktavardhaka, raktashodhaka, Kasahara, shwasahara, hikkani-grahana, mootrala, vrishya, kusthaghna, jwaraghna, vishamjwarapratibandhaka, balya, rasyana, garbhashayasankochaka.*

Chemical composition: Piperine, piperlonguminine, piperlongumine, methyl-3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamate. The fruit part consists of volatile oil (1%), protein, starch, alkaloids, saponins, carbohydrates and amygdalin, a waxy alkaloid N-isobutyldeca-trans-2-trans-4-dienamide, calcium, phosphorus, iron and a terpenoid substance. Lignans and esters such as sesamin, pulvatuilol, fargesin, Z-12-octadecenoic-glycerol-monoester, tridecyl-dihydro-p-coumarate and eicosanyl-(E)-p-coumarate.

Pharmacological and clinical study of *Pippali*: Antibacterial, Antimicrobial, Anti-amoebic, anti-diabetic, neuroprotective, immunomodulatory, anti-tumour, anti-oxidant, antiplatelet, antifertility, anti-

asthmatic, Anthelmintic, Anti-snake venom, Acaricidal, Antiulcer.

3. *Haritaki*^[9]

Rogagnata: *Swasa, Kasa, Prameha, Arsha, Kushta, Udara Krimi, Shotha, Vaisvarya, Grahani Roga, Vibandha, Visham Javar, Gulam, Aadhmana, Trisha, Chhardhi, Hikka, Kandu, Hridya Roga, Kamala, Shola, Aanaha, Pleeha Roga, Yakrut Roga, Ashmari, Mutrakrichha, Mutraghata, Udavarta, Pandu Roga, Mada, Shiroroga, Atisara, Arochaka, Kaphapreshaka, Klaibya, Angavasada, Srotovibandha, Pralepa, Pramoha.*

Karma: *Deepani, Medhya, Rasayani, Chakshushya, Bruhmani, Ayushya, Anulomani.*

Chemical composition: Triterpenes arjunglucoside I, arjungenin, and the chebulosides I and II, chebulin, phenolic compounds including ellagic acid, 2,4-chebulyl- β -D-glucopyranose, chebulinic acid, gallic acid, ethyl gallate, punicalagin, terflavin A, terchebin, luteolin, and tannic acid, Chebulic acid, Luteic acid, terflavin B, a type of tannin, chebulinic acid. other minor compounds include corilegin, β -D-glucogallin, glucose and sorbitol.

Pharmacological and clinical study of *Haritaki*:

Antitussive, Anti-diabetic, Cardio-protective, Hepato-protective, Anti-ulcerogenic & wound healing activity, Anti-arthritic, Anti-mutagenic and anti-carcinogenic, Anti-viral, Radio-protective, Mild laxative, Antihelmintic, Antiplasmodial, antispasmodic Immunomodulatory.

4. *Guda*

In *Brihatrayi*, Charaka has given guna of *Guda*, i.e. The *Krimi-Majja-shyonit-Meda-Mamsavardhak*, *Annapanavidhiadhyaya* in *Sutrasthana*. *Alpa doshkar* is the final prepared shudhha *Guda*. *Sushruta* has mentioned *Guda* and its properties in *sutrasthana adhyaya* 45, *Dravdravya vidhyaninya shlok* no.160. *Guna karma* of *Naveen* and *Puran Guda* was separately mentioned by *shushurta*. *Asthangsangrahkara* mentioned *Guda* in *Sutrasthana, dravdravyavdhyaniya, shlok* 87 (*As.Su* 6/87). He explained more or same uses as *Astangahriday* like in *jwara, swasa, Kasa, hikka, swarabheda, aruchi, arsha, Grahani, pandu, udara, pleeha* and *rasayana* in combination with other drug or solitary. *Bhavaprakasha Samhita* written by Acharya *Bhava Mishra*. *Guda* is described at *Nighantu* part of *samhita* in *Ikshu-varga*. *Naveen Guda* properties are mentioned as *Vrushya, Guru, Snigdha, Vatanashak, Mutrashodhan, Na-ati-pittakara, Medakara, Kaphakara, Krimikara, Balakara, Swasakara* and *Puran Guda* is *Laghu, Pathya, Anbhishandi, Agnijanaka, Pusthikruta, Pittaghna, Madhur, Vrushya, Vataghna, Raktaprasadaka*.

Chemical Composition: Sucrose: 50%, Invert sugars: 20% of jaggery, Moisture and other insoluble matters: 20% of jaggery is moisture and other insoluble matters,

such as wood ash, proteins, and bagasse fibers. Jaggery is a good source of minerals like calcium, phosphorous, and iron. Jaggery contains vitamins A, B1, B2, B5, B6, C, D2, E, and PP.

Pharmacological Action: Jaggery contains dietary fiber that can aid in promoting regular bowel movements and easing the passage of stool.

DISCUSSION

The action of *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya* etc. get neutralized among themselves. Therefore, stronger component neutralizes the action of weaker component. Hence, action of particular drug compound is the action 'as a whole and slow in nature'. *Trivritadi Gutika* contains mainly *Katu*, *tikta rasa*, *laghu*, *ruksha*, *Tikshna guna*, *Madhura vipaka* and also *ushana veerya*.

Mode of Action in *Vibandha* (Constipation)

The *ushna virya* and *tikshna guna* of *Trivruta* and *Haritaki* directly break down accumulated stools and stimulate peristalsis. These herbs alleviate *Ama* (undigested toxins) and *Kapha* blockage, removing obstacles in the digestive channels. *Haritaki* and *pippali* enhances gut motility and supports gut lining integrity through anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.

Mode of Action in *Udavarta*

Udavarta manifests as upward-moving *Vata*, seen clinically as bloating, abdominal pain, and vomiting. Here, the strong *virechana* (purgative) action of *Trivruta* rebalances *Vata* by expelling accumulated doshas downward. Thus, *Trivrutadi Gutika* promotes *Vatanulomana* (normal downward movement of *Vata*), alleviating symptoms of *Udavarta*.

Table 3: Mode of Action of Trivritadi Gutika.

Condition	Mechanism	Herbal Effects
<i>Vibandha</i>	<i>Anulomana</i> (downward flow), <i>Mukha-samvahana</i>	<i>Haritaki</i> , <i>Pippali</i> cleanse channels; <i>Trivrut</i> purges stool; <i>Guda</i> soothes.
<i>Udavarta</i>	<i>Vatanulomana</i> via gentle purgation	<i>Ushna virya</i> resets <i>Vata</i> direction; coordinated elimination

CONCLUSION

Trivrutadi Gutika acts as a gentle purgative (*sukha-virechana*), perfect for clearing *Vata* and *Ama*. It Restores normal downward flow of *Vata* (*Vatanulomana*), essential in both *Vibandha* and *Udavarta*.

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